

A Biological Perspective of Viola-Jones Face Detection

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Abstract – Human face detection in digital images and videos is a mature technology, yet its operational performance is generally sub-optimal. Any improvement would be beneficial in many applications. Some computer vision approaches to object recognition, including face detection, have begun to achieve impressive levels of accuracy and robustness, yet lack a clear connection to known cortical constructs. This motivates investigations of biologically-inspired techniques. The mechanisms by which contour shapes, and in particular faces, are represented in cortex and the means that neural models and computer vision algorithms can more closely approximate these are examined. The OpenCV library implements a standard face detection solution, the Viola-Jones detector. A hybrid framework, with a truncated Viola-Jones cascade followed by neural population models, is considered in this current work.

Keywords – face detection; Viola-Jones; biological vision; V1; V4; neural network

I. INTRODUCTION

The detection of (principally human) faces in digital images or videos, often as a component of a broader face, emotion, or pose recognition system, is a mature technology. However, its operational performance, even in less difficult frontal face tests, is generally sub-optimal. These deficiencies are critical in many applications, particularly when this function is a preliminary component of a full recognition architecture, as the detection itself is often seen as the processing bottleneck [1]. These include implementation within an embedded system or mobile application, exploiting the highly parallel structure and efficiency of a Graphics Processing

Unit (GPU)-enabled device. Any improvement would be beneficial in many applications, particularly in those with a low tolerance for error – security, surveillance, fraud detection, assistive devices, etc. [2].

The representation of contour shape is an essential component of object recognition, including faces. Human observers are exceptionally sensitive to changes in contour shape [3], and this capacity develops in early infancy [4]. However, the cortical mechanisms underlying shape analysis and object recognition are incompletely understood, leaving this a fundamental open question in neuroscience.

Some computer vision approaches to object recognition have begun to achieve impressive levels of accuracy and robustness, yet lack a clear connection to known cortical constructs. There is no accepted neurobiological theory as to how object recognition, and the underlying analysis of shape, is accomplished. Such an understanding would be useful theoretically as well as in developing or improving face detection methodologies and applications. The mechanisms by which contour shapes, and in particular faces, are represented in cortex and the means that neural models and computer vision algorithms can more closely approximate these are considered.

The OpenCV library is widely used in the image processing community. It implements a standard face detection solution, commonly known as the Viola-Jones detector [5]. Despite its overall superior performance and desirable properties, empirical evidence has shown that the Viola-Jones methodology may be improved upon. The goal of maximizing its already high detection rates while preserving or decreasing its already low false alarm rates and exceptional execution times has motivated

Figure 1. Haar-like features.

investigations of alterations. Specifically, after finding that a number of true faces are rejected before the final stage, the hypothesis of a diminishing return with the full Viola-Jones rejection cascade is posited.

This idea fosters interest in biologically-inspired techniques. The approach developed is a hybrid framework, with a truncated Viola-Jones cascade followed by neural population models. In this current work, we explore the initial and intermediate stages of these neural areas, with the supposition that detected faces could be increased and missed faces could be decreased when compared to a standard Viola-Jones implementation.

An attempt to draw correlations between biology and image processing is made. In doing so, a convergence of neural models and computer vision algorithms is sought, with awareness that nature has found efficient solutions to vision problems. In particular, beginning with the retina, the primate ventral (shape recognition) pathway in the occipital and temporal lobes extending hierarchically from primary visual cortex (V1) through the intermediate visual area 4 (V4) to the inferotemporal cortex (IT), is considered. In selecting appropriate biological paradigms, cellular response properties (i.e., receptive field complexity and size), seen as the ventral pathway is traversed, are faithfully interpreted. Cortical representations of contour shape moving from distributed to compact are observed, with an attempt to relate these neurophysiological findings to computer algorithms.

In area V1, particular attention is paid to the similarity between the responses of biological cells and the Haar wavelets employed in the Viola-Jones rejection cascade. Downstream, visual cortical neurons in monkey extrastriate cortex are sensitive to the fine structure of contour shape. Units in area V2 respond differentially to a variety of local contour configurations including angles, arcs and

intersections [6, 7]. In area V4, cells that are selective for a particular local shape configuration at a particular location on the contour within a larger shape have been described [8]. For example, one neuron might prefer contours with a sharp concavity at the northwest corner; another unit might be selective for contours with a shallow convexity at the southernmost tip. The response profiles of these cells are further modulated by the local contour configurations at neighboring locations on the contour. Thus, the unit preferring a sharp concavity at the NW corner might be potentiated by a sharp concavity located immediately clockwise along the contour, or suppressed by a convexity located immediately counterclockwise. It has been demonstrated that a population of such V4 units can provide a detailed description of the contour shape [9].

We construct a simulated population of V4-like units with sensitivities to local curvature, relative location of the contour configuration on the contour, distance of the contour configuration from the center of mass, and convexity / concavity and consider their recognition abilities and ways of demonstrating it. Stimuli (faces with 2-dimensional closed contours representing boundaries) evoke a pattern of activity across the population of V4-like cells, distinct from non-face presentations.

II. METHODOLOGY

The Viola-Jones detector [5] is a binary classifier. It produces a “face” or “no face” decision for a particular region-of-interest (R.O.I.) at a specific location and scale in an image for each stage in its rejection cascade, yielding a high detection rate (low false negatives) and a low rejection rate (high false positives). Search regions of different sizes are swept over the original image – a depth-first paradigm with the output of each stage being the position and scale of each “face”, or alternatively the “no face” decision. It utilizes Haar-like input features. These are essentially Haar wavelets – sequences of rescaled square-shaped functions together forming a basis. These can be seen as adjacent or overlapping rectangular regions at a specific position and scale in a detection window, where the weights multiplied by the areas sum to zero. The image features then become the responses to these rectangular filters. In constructing the rejection cascade, there are approximately 60,000 different Haar features to choose from. Large, yet insignificant when compared to V1’s approximately 190 million neurons [10].

Figure 2. Curvature filters.

The Viola-Jones detector also employs boosting and classification using the AdaBoost learning algorithm [11]. This technique of statistical boosting entails the supervised learning of a strong classifier (the full cascade) out of many weak and simple classifiers (each stage of the cascade), ordered from least to most complex. The end result of the supervised training is a series of Haar-like features ordered to yield the desired performance parameters. For the present work, OpenCV’s standard, out-of-the-box pre-trained Haar cascade frontal face XML is used [12]. This provides the complete description of every stage, tree, rectangle, threshold, etc., for the entire cascade. Here, the rejection cascade of binary classifiers (“face” vs. “no face”) is constructed using the Haar-like input features with high detection rates and low rejection rates at each stage, with each stage composed of multiple decisions. Each node in the decision tree is a Haar-like feature evaluated against a threshold. The final classifier, an efficient feature selector, is a linear combination of weak classifiers – the features.

Functionally, multiple position- and scale-dependent regions-of-interest of an image are presented to the Viola-Jones rejection cascade, with each stage computing a “face” or “no face” decision based upon applications of multiple simple Haar-like feature filters. Results are summed and thresholded. There are an increasing number of individual decision trees within each subsequent stage.

Stand-alone models of V4-like units are developed to evaluate recognition performance. Simple image processing techniques are used to decompose an image into independent closed-contour silhouettes. Shapes are represented as sets of points sampled from the shape contours. For each image, contours are extracted using the numerical gradient, and a determination of a set of boundary points with oriented tangents is made. The result is a parametric description ($x(t)$, $y(t)$, and $\text{tangent}(t)$) of each contour.

For each point along the contour, its angle ($0^\circ - 360^\circ$) relative to and distance (in pixels) from the image’s center of attention (center of mass, centroid, center of image) is computed. For consistency, the contour’s points are considered such that each contour begins at approximately 3 o’clock and proceeds counterclockwise.

Using the parametric forms $x(t)$ and $y(t)$, the curvature can be extracted [13] and smoothed (regularized), resulting in the discrete curvature, parameterized by the Gaussian space constant. It should be noted that the curvature of the pre-digitized object cannot be calculated exactly. It can only be estimated, with a lower bound on the error of the achievable measurement [14]. The *direction of curvature* is defined to be orthogonal to the tangent and to point towards the interior of the closed contour [15]. It is computed using the orientation and inverse tangent.

Next, each contour is segmented into iso-curvature regions. This approach is computationally tractable and connects conceptually to previous models of “parts-based” recognition [16, 17, 18]. However, there is no theoretical need for this initial segmentation stage – a large population of V4-like cells could describe overlapping regions of the contour in an over-complete representation. Once an iso-curvature segment is defined, all points on the segment can be thought of as having the same curvature value. For each iso-curvature segment of each image, feature vectors composed of mean polar angle of contour region (e.g., 3 o’clock is assigned to be 0 radians, 12 o’clock is assigned to be $\pi / 2$ radians, etc.), mean curvature of the region, mean direction of curvature of the region, and mean distance from the center of mass of the region, are created. These features all have approximate neurobiological correlates in area V4 and other extrastriate areas [19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 8, 9].

All models are constructed using the MATLAB application development environment version 8.2.0.701 R2013b [25] and Microsoft Visual C++ 2010 [26]. Version 2.4.2 of the OpenCV [11] library’s standard Viola-Jones face detection implementation – widely used in the image processing community – is used as well.

III. RESULTS

Haar-like features are shown in **Figure 1**. The first 16 trees of stage 21 of the default frontal face cascade provided by OpenCV are depicted. A comparison with [27] reveals a great deal of

similarity between primary visual cortex (V1) receptive fields and the features used for the Viola-Jones rejection cascade, with emergent face “candidates” seen as top-down attentional loci [28].

A rendering of typical curvature filters, actualized in visual area 4 (V4) or in the biologically-inspired model explored in the present work, is shown in **Figure 2**.

IV. DISCUSSION

Downstream, the response properties of inferotemporal cortical (IT) cells – namely nonlinearly integrated groups of curvatures (posterior) and large-scale whole-scene feature integration (anterior) – and cells of the fusiform gyrus cells, particularly the fusiform face area (FFA), may be considered for face detection in the wild.

V. CONCLUSION

Our preliminary results suggest that curvature- and position-sensitive units, as seen in area V4, can function as robust shape descriptors used in face detection. By constructing computer network models, the utility of cells with response properties similar to those found in V4 (and in downstream areas) will be demonstrated by successfully subjecting them to artificial recognition tasks on a set of real face or negative images. In so doing, a connection between a computer model of a recognition system and known cortical mechanisms within a biologically realistic network architecture will be established.

VI. REFERENCES

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